

detected in the F₂ of crosses among susceptible parents.

Of the eight resistance genes found in IR1905-81-3-1 and IR3259-PP5-160-1, and nine genes in IR3259-PP8-172-7, the

gene conferring resistance to race IH-1 (isolate PO7-10) seems to be linked to the gene resistant to race II-1. The two genes giving resistance to race IB-45 did not segregate independently from the two

genes resistant to race ID-15 or from that acting against race IH-1 (isolate 43); the remaining genes showed no linkage. The six resistance genes in Pai-kan-tao segregated independently. □

Resistance of five IR varieties to tungro

E. R. Tiongco, R. C. Cabunagan, and H. Hibino, IRR

IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56 resistance to tungro was determined by mass screening and test tube inoculation methods.

The five IR varieties and TN1 (susceptible check) were inoculated in a cage with 1, 3, and 4 insects/seedling using the tungro mass screening method. Seedling infection increased as insects increased from 1 to 5/seedling (see figure). TN1 always had the highest percentage of infection, regardless of the number of insects per seedling; followed by IR42, IR36, IR56, and IR50. IR54 showed the lowest seedling infection, but infection level was not significantly different from that of IR50 and IR56.

By the reaction scale for tungro, IR36 and IR42 changed their reaction from resistant to susceptible when the number of insects per seedling was increased from 1 to 5. IR50, IR54, and IR56 reaction changed from resistant to intermediate (see table).

Seven-day-old seedlings were each inoculated with 1, 3, and 5 insects, using the test tube inoculation method. Again, percentage of infected seedlings increased with number of insects per seedling (see figure). However, at even 1 insect/seedling, IR36, IR42, and TN1 were susceptible. IR50, IR54, and IR56 had an intermediate reaction (see table). The highest percentage of infection using the test tube inoculation method, regardless of number of insects, may be caused by the insects' forced feeding on the seedling in confinement.

These results indicate possible unstable tungro resistance in some IR varieties. In the field, degree of resistance decreases with increased disease and insect pressure. This is apparent on varieties with tungro resistance conditioned only by resistance to the vector insect.

Percentage seedling infection of 5 tungro-resistant IR varieties inoculated with different numbers of tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens* per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.

Tungro reaction of 5 IR varieties inoculated by 1, 3, or 5 insects per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.^a

Variety	Mass screening			Test tube inoculation		
	1	3	5	1	3	5
IR36	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR42	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	I	I	I	I	S
IR54	R	R	I	I	I	S
IR56	R	I	I	I	I	S
TN1	I	S	S	S	S	S

^aBased on the scale for RTV mass screening of resistant (R) = 0-30% seedling infection, intermediate (I) = 31-60% seedling infection, susceptible (S) = 61-100% seedling infection.

Reaction of rice varieties to blast and brown spot diseases at Ponnampet

K. T. Pandurangowda, N. A. Janardhanagowda, and R. C. Yaraguntaiah, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya, India

An experiment at the Ponnampet Agricultural Research Station, during 1982 kharif identified varieties resistant to

blast and brown spot diseases. The National Screening Nursery evaluated 334 entries under nursery and transplanted condition. The nursery followed the uniform blast nursery pattern.

Twenty-eight entries had resistance to blast and brown spot (Table 1). Seventy-eight were resistant to leaf blast 83 to neck blast, and 223 to brown spot (Table 2). □

Table 1. Rice with resistance to blast and brown spot diseases, Mandya, India.

Pedigree	
TR20/Co 29	IET 8159
Ratna Mutant	Acham/IR20
IET6080	Ar 10-169 Mutant
Hema/CR57/Vikram/Shakti/ORSTR952	CR151-79/CR1014
CR151/CR1014	Tellahamsa/W12708
IET6288	WGL 16085/Kakatiya
IET6314	Imp. Sona/Pak. Basmati
Cul-240/IR20	IET6314/Co 2
Lalnakanda/IR30	IR32/Swarnadhan
IR8/Co 25	OS4/Palguna
Dorpandy mutant	IR8/IET4141
IET7810	IET4699/Ras 370
IR2061-465-1-5-IR36	IET4699/Bas 370
Hamsraj/Saket 4	IET7748

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Table 2. Reaction of rice varieties to blast symptoms and brown spot disease at Mandya, India.

Scale ^a	Entries (no.)		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
0-3	78	83	223
4-6	213	217	99
7-9	43	34	12

^aScale: 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible.

IR36, a promising variety for bacterial blight-prone areas of Haryana

S. A. Malik, H. A. U. Regional Research Station, Uchani, Karnal; S. C. Ahuja, H. A. U. Rice Research Station, Kaul, Kurukshetra; and C. V. S. Malik, H. A. U. Directorate of Research, Hissar, India

IR36 is a semidwarf, medium-maturity rice variety with slender grains and bacterial blight (BB) resistance. In 1981, it was recommended by the central variety release committee for commercial cultivation in India. Varietal trials under BB stress were conducted in 1980-82 kharif at Kaul and Karnal stations.

Performance of IR36 under bacterial blight stress in Haryana, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha) during kharif				Duration (days)	Panicles/m ²	Length-breadth ratio	BB reaction ^a
	1980 (Kaul)	1981 (Karnal)	1982 (Karnal)	Mean				
IR36	5.6	7.0	5.2	5.9	135	269	2.95	3
Jaya	4.4	7.4	6.2	6.0	148	251	2.32	9
PR106	4.3	6.3	5.1	5.2	149	213	2.60	9
Palman 579	4.5	6.8	5.5	5.6	130	243	2.90	5
CD	0.85	0.56	0.89					
CV(%)	11.12	4.0	11.0					

^aBy 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

IR36 yielded better than PR106 and Palman 579 checks and was equal to Jaya (see table). IR36 had more panicles per square meter, and higher length-breadth ratio than all three checks. It matured

earlier than Jaya, which would allow good performance in wheat - rice rotation. BB infestation in 1981 and 1982 kharif was not as high as in 1980 kharif. □

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India

K. T. Pandurang Gowda, S. Kumaraswamy, and R. C. Yaraguntaiah, Plant Pathology Department, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya, India

Blast (B1), brown spot (BS), grain discoloration (GD), and udbatta (UDb) diseases are becoming important in

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India, 1982 kharif.

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	B1		BS	GD	UDb
	Leaf	Neck			
KMS8	R	R	R	R	S
IET6265	R	M	R	M	R
KMS9	R	R	R	R	R
KMS4	R	R	M	R	R
RP850	R	M	R	R	R
KMS7	R	R	R	R	R
KMP66	R	M	M	R	M

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